

THE RELATIONSHIP MODEL BETWEEN THE JUDICIAL COMMISSION AND THE SUPREME COURT FOR INTEGRATED JUDICIAL OVERSIGHT

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Abstract

This research is motivated by the condition that there is an ongoing debate to date regarding the supervisory function carried out by the Supreme Court (MA) and the Judicial Commission (KY), especially to what extent supervision is not only on the behavior of judges (misconduct), but can also reach technical and judicial substance (legal error). This study aims to formulate an ideal model of the division of authority that can strengthen the independence and accountability of judicial power. The research method used is normative juridical with a philosophical approach, a legislative approach, a conceptual approach, and a comparative approach. Research data was obtained through a literature study of laws and regulations, court decisions, legal literature, and related official documents, which were then analyzed qualitatively to obtain a comprehensive picture of the research problem. The results of the study indicate that. The division of authority of the Judicial Commission and the Supreme Court has a clear legal basis, namely Article 24A and 24B of the 1945 Constitution, Law Number 18 of 2011 concerning the Judicial Commission, and Law Number 5 of 2004 in conjunction with Law Number 3 of 2009 concerning the Supreme Court. However, in practice there is still overlapping authority, especially in the implementation of supervision and the imposition of sanctions. The recommended ideal model is a clear, synergistic, and complementary division of functions, with the Judicial Commission as an external supervisor and the Supreme Court as an internal supervisor, accompanied by an effective and measurable coordination mechanism.

Keywords: Judicial Supervision, Judicial Commission, Supreme Court, Judicial Oversight.

INTRODUCTION

The amendment to the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia (UUD 1945) affirms the nature and character of judicial power by stating that "judicial power is the power of an independent state to administer justice to uphold law and justice." In Law No. 48 of 2009 concerning judicial power, it is stated that "judicial power is the power of an independent state to administer justice to uphold law and justice based on Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution."

The Supreme Court (MA), as one of the pinnacles of judicial power, holds a strategic position and role in the field of judicial power, as it oversees not only the four judicial environments but also administrative, personnel, and financial management, as well as facilities and infrastructure. The one-roof policy presents responsibilities and challenges because the MA is required to demonstrate its ability to create a professional, effective, transparent, and accountable institutional organization. (Rumadan, 2016) The consequence of the unification of the Supreme Court would be that it would grant the Supreme Court vast powers, raising concerns about a monopoly of judicial power. Therefore, efforts were made to limit this

authority by establishing the Judges' Honorary Council (DKH), which has the authority to oversee the behavior of judges, issue recommendations, promote and transfer judges, and draft a code of ethics for judges. Rumadan, 2016) The formation of this judges' honorary council was the forerunner to the formation of the Judicial Commission, which then, during the third amendment to the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, included the addition of one article in the chapter on judicial power, namely Article 24B concerning the Judicial Commission. The phenomenon of judges' decisions today, many of which have received sharp criticism and public scrutiny because they are considered dry and do not yet reflect the values of justice as mandated by the 1945 Constitution as amended by Article 24 paragraph (1) which emphasizes that the judicial power (where the product is the judge's decision) is an independent power to administer justice to uphold law and justice. This criticism must be placed proportionally, so that not only the judges and their decisions are the target of criticism, without seeing the fundamental problems in the law enforcement system in our country which cause the principle of justice not to be realized optimally.

The Indonesian judiciary consists of three state institutions, as mentioned in the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia: the Supreme Court, the Constitutional Court, and the Judicial Commission. The Supreme Court and the Constitutional Court are the only state institutions that carry out judicial functions, while the Judicial Commission serves as an auxiliary institution for the judicial function in Indonesia. The Judicial Commission is a state institution specifically established to oversee the performance of judges and to propose the appointment of Supreme Court justices in Indonesia. The formation of the Judicial Commission is essentially a mandate of the constitution as formulated in Article 24 A paragraph (3) and 24 B of the 1945 Constitution. Article 24 A paragraph (3) states: "Candidates for Supreme Court Justices are proposed by the Judicial Commission to the House of Representatives to obtain approval and are then appointed as supreme court justices by the President." Furthermore, Article 24 B states: "(1) The Judicial Commission is independent and has the authority to propose the appointment of supreme court justices and has other authority in order to maintain and uphold the honor, dignity, and behavior of judges. (2) Members of the Judicial Commission must have knowledge and experience in the legal field and have integrity and a personality that is beyond reproach. (3) Members of the Judicial Commission are appointed and dismissed by the President with the approval of the House of Representatives. (4) The composition, position, and membership of the Judicial Commission are regulated by law.

To implement the mandate of Article 24B of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, Law Number 22 of 2004 concerning the Judicial Commission was then passed, which was then revised by the enactment of Law Number 18 of 2011 concerning Amendments to Law Number 22 of 2004 concerning the Judicial Commission (KY Law). The changes to this legal product were made in order to improve and adjust to the situation and conditions regarding the dynamics of monitoring the behavior of judges in the regions. One of the striking changes is the implementation of Judicial Commission Liaisons in the regions. This provision states that the Judicial Commission can appoint liaisons in the regions according to the needs in order to support the implementation of the Judicial Commission's duties. The Judicial Commission is a state institution whose recognition is regulated by the constitution, thus

holding a very strong position. Its authority is stipulated in Article 24B of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia. Law No. 18 of 2011 (amending Law No. 22 of 2004 concerning the Judicial Commission). However, the Judicial Commission's powers tend not to be completed in one go, as they still require follow-up action from other institutions. For example, in the selection of Supreme Court justice candidates, the Judicial Commission is tasked with and authorized to propose Supreme Court justice candidates. However, ultimately, the Judicial Commission's proposal can still be rejected by the House of Representatives (DPR). In practice, the DPR has once rejected the names proposed by the Judicial Commission, even though a number of prominent public figures had been involved in the selection process.

Article 24B of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia tends to position the Judicial Commission as a watchdog designed solely to find fault with judges rather than as a sparring partner capable of finding fault but also rewarding achievements and even championing their welfare. In addition to proposing the appointment of Supreme Court justices, Article 24B of the 1945 Constitution grants the Judicial Commission only the authority to safeguard and uphold the honor, dignity, and behavior of judges. This authority was translated into a form of oversight that was not optimally designed by the Judicial Commission Law, resulting in it being declared contrary to the 1945 Constitution by the Constitutional Court. This differs from the Italian constitution, for example, where, in addition to the authority to appoint and dismiss judges and take disciplinary action, the Superior Council of the Judiciary also has the authority to transfer and promote judges. Thus, the role of the Judicial Commission is not only preventive-repressive, but also consultative-protective. That is why in some countries the nomenclature for the Judicial Commission is the Judicial Service Commission. This service function for judges is not regulated in our constitution. The Judicial Commission Law should be amended to address this function in the future. In addition to its oversight role, the Judicial Commission, as an institution that upholds the honor, dignity, and conduct of judges, also has the authority to discipline judges found to have violated the code of ethics. As an institution that balances judicial power, the Judicial Commission should be strengthened, both in terms of its authority and the objects of its oversight. (Wajdi, 2020)

There is ongoing debate regarding the oversight function performed by the Supreme Court and the Judicial Commission, particularly the extent to which oversight extends beyond judicial misconduct to judicial technicalities and substance (legal errors). The primary argument often cited is the provision that oversight must not diminish the judge's freedom to examine a case. Therefore, it is interesting to examine the importance of the relationship model between the Judicial Commission and the Supreme Court in realizing integrated judicial oversight. This research will culminate in recommendations regarding the relationship model between the Judicial Commission and the Supreme Court within the concept of integrated judicial oversight.

RESEARCH METHODS

In this study, the type of research used is normative legal research, namely research that focuses on studying the rules or norms in positive law. (Nasution, 2008). The approaches used are: philosophical approach, statutory approach, conceptual approach, and comparative approach.

Types and sources of data include: primary legal materials, secondary legal materials, and tertiary legal materials. This study examines secondary data consisting of primary legal materials and secondary legal materials collected using bibliography study and document study techniques. (Muhaimin, 2020) All legal materials obtained are then analyzed and processed using prescriptive normative analysis methods. Conclusions or drawing conclusions in this study use the deductive method, namely drawing conclusions from the general to the specific.

DISCUSSION

1. Model of Relationship between the Judicial Commission and the Supreme Court

Incidents and events that could undermine and distort the relationship between the Judicial Commission and the Supreme Court in the past must not be repeated in the future and cannot be allowed to continue and considered trivial, because this can have an impact on the unproductive performance of both state institutions which in turn can harm the interests of the wider community, especially the community seeking justice. Therefore, it is inevitable to address and seek alternative solutions, so that the quality of law enforcement and justice in the future will be increasingly better and its benefits will be felt by the community, nation and state. The alignment of the Supreme Court's authority with the Judicial Commission must be based on the philosophy of the Pancasila State of Law. Philipus M. Hadjon introduced the concept of the Pancasila State of Law, whose "elements are drawn from the state thought of the founders of this Republic and returned to Pancasila as the philosophical basis of the state," which "prioritizes the principle of harmonious relations between the government and the people based on the principle of harmony." (Hadjon, 1993)

One of the elements of the Pancasila Legal State is the establishment of proportional functional relationships between state powers, where all powers in the state are directed towards the happiness of the people together in accordance with the basic idea of the state's goals outlined in the Preamble to the 1945 Constitution. Thus, it is hoped that there will be no unhealthy struggle or competition between one power and another, so that there is no need for a strict separation because between one power and another there is a proportional and reasonable functional relationship. Finding an ideal pattern of relationship or relationship between the Judicial Commission and the Supreme Court is a challenge for both institutions in order to create a harmonious relationship in carrying out the duties and responsibilities of supervising the dignity and behavior of judges.

Philosophically, the officials of these two state institutions should first understand and be aware of their respective existence, duties, and authorities, and mutually understand the existence of the duties and authorities of other state institutions. The Supreme Court was born and established as an attribute of a state based on law to uphold law and justice. Its constitutional philosophy is to represent the state in realizing the values of truth and justice within the state. Likewise, the Judicial Commission is a *conditio sine qua non* (condition sine qua non) of existence and was born as an attribute of a state based on law and democracy to oversee and partner with the Supreme Court in upholding substantive law and justice. At a minimum, the above paradigm must be established and agreed upon by the leaders and members of both state

institutions, both conceptually and in practice. (Juanda, 2021) The arrangement of the relationship between the Supreme Court and the Judicial Commission must begin with restoring the natural order of the Judicial Commission and the Supreme Court based on the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia. The Judicial Commission and the Supreme Court are important pillars in maintaining the honor, dignity, and behavior of judges in the judicial system in Indonesia. In the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, the Supreme Court is given the authority as the highest judicial institution (Article 24A) while the Judicial Commission is given the mandate to maintain and uphold the honor, dignity, and behavior of judges (Article 24B). The Supreme Court's nature is adjudication, where its decisions are authoritative because they are made by judges free from intervention by any party. In this context, the Judicial Powers Law states that "any interference in judicial matters by parties outside the judicial authority is prohibited, except in cases as referred to in the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia."

The nature of the Judicial Commission is that it is an independent institution authorized to propose the appointment of supreme court judges and has other powers in order to maintain and uphold the honor, dignity, and behavior of judges. In the context of supervision, the scope of supervision by the Judicial Commission is ethics, not law enforcement or administrative supervision, as stated in the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia. In the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia there is no dichotomy between technical judicial supervision and ethical supervision of judges, because both are complementary to realize a clean and just judiciary, not competitive in nature that weakens each other's role.

In carrying out their duties and functions, the Supreme Court and the Judicial Commission should be critical partners, maintaining mutual respect while still being able to critique each other's policies and performance. Therefore, the relationship between the Supreme Court and the Judicial Commission should be built on a shared goal: to uphold the dignity and integrity of the judiciary through a mutual understanding of each institution's core duties and performance limitations. If any gray areas arise, internal consolidation must be initiated immediately, avoiding retaliatory statements in the mass media that could further aggravate the situation and lead to a decline in public trust in the judiciary. The Supreme Court also recognizes that its relationship with the Judicial Commission is not yet optimal. This is contained in the 2010-2035 judicial reform blueprint, namely the Redefinition of the Relationship between the Supreme Court and the Judicial Commission as Partners in the Implementation of the Supervisory Function. Redefining and improving coordination and cooperation with the Judicial Commission is an important agenda, namely by carrying out: (Supreme Court, 2010)

- a. Equal partnership relationships by increasing cooperation, including joint implementation of supervisory activities.
- b. Establishment of common standards and guidelines in the supervision and examination of alleged violations of judicial behavior, which include: coordination mechanisms in the supervision of judicial behavior activities, both between the Judicial Commission and the Supreme Court, as well as between the Judicial Commission and judicial bodies under the

Supreme Court, mechanisms for submitting recommendations for disciplinary punishment by the Judicial Commission and the determination of disciplinary punishment by the Supreme Court, mechanisms for the formation and examination by the Judges' Honorary Council, guarantees of rights and legal certainty for parties who are the object of supervision or examination, and minimum standards for the implementation of supervision and examination activities in order to accommodate the principles of objectivity and accountability of supervision activities.

- c. Affirmation of the independence of judges and courts by drafting amendments to the Supreme Court Law, the Judicial Body Law and the Judicial Commission Law and carrying out strategic activities to encourage the elimination of provisions containing elements of: assessment of the sound of judges' decisions, imbalance in the process of supervision and discipline of judges, and the potential to give rise to multiple interpretations related to the supervisory authority held by the MA's internal supervisors and external supervisory institutions.

In line with the above, one of the most important things to create a harmonious relationship between the Supreme Court and the Judicial Commission is the need to build a good communication model with the principle of mutual respect, and listening to each other with the principle of openness and without mutual suspicion. Good prejudice between the Supreme Court and the Judicial Commission must be developed through a system/policy in the form of statutory regulations in order to realize an independent judicial power in order to uphold law and justice as mandated in Article 24 paragraph (1) of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia. The relationship between the Judicial Commission and the Supreme Court should be built on a common goal: to uphold the dignity and integrity of the judiciary, with each party understanding the core duties and limitations of their respective roles. If any areas of uncertainty arise, internal consolidation should be initiated to find a better solution. Finding this ideal relationship is a challenge for both institutions going forward, ensuring a harmonious relationship in carrying out their duties and responsibilities of overseeing the dignity and conduct of judges in carrying out their noble duties. Based on this, the author proposes that this harmonization be realized in the form of structuring the relationship between the Supreme Court and the Judicial Commission, namely "A Coordinative-Consultative Relationship Model Based on the Value of Musyarah Mufakat"

The relationship between the Judicial Commission and the Supreme Court in supervising judges can be built through a coordinative-consultative model, namely a relationship pattern that prioritizes cooperation, equality of function and mutual respect for the authority of each institution in maintaining the integrity of judicial power. Coordination means the Judicial Commission and the Supreme Court actively coordinate with each other in implementing judicial oversight, ensuring effective, efficient, targeted, and non-overlapping oversight. Consultative means the Judicial Commission and the Supreme Court hold consultations to address differing perceptions regarding report handling and recommend action against judges suspected of violating the code of ethics for judicial conduct. This model is based on the value of deliberation and consensus while respecting judicial independence. The fourth principle of

Pancasila states, "Democracy guided by the wisdom of deliberation/representation." This means that the principle of deliberation and consensus is prioritized through representatives and representative bodies in fighting for the people's mandate. A closer look at the meaning and significance of the fourth principle is as follows: (Yusdiyanto, 2016)

- a) The essence of this principle is democracy, namely government of the people, by the people, and for the people.
- b) Deliberation, namely making a unanimous decision, carried out together through wisdom.
- c) Implementing decisions based on honesty. Decisions are unanimous, resulting in shared honest consequences. The value of identity is deliberation.
- d) It embodies the principle of democracy, namely a sense of love for the people, fighting for the people's ideals, and possessing a people-centered spirit. The principle of deliberation for consensus, namely paying attention to and respecting the aspirations of all people through deliberative forums, appreciating differences, and prioritizing the interests of the people, nation, and state.

Thus, in a condensed form, the fourth principle of Pancasila contains elements such as the element of democracy, the element of deliberation, and the element of popular sovereignty. These three elements that make up the fourth principle have different positions. Where the element of popular sovereignty is the incarnation of the two previous elements: the element of democracy and the element of deliberation. The other two elements, democracy and deliberation, are originally the spiritual foundations of the fourth principle itself, as well as the political basis transformed into the element of popular sovereignty. (Usman, 2020) The principle of democracy guided by the wisdom of deliberation/representation is based on the principles of Belief in One Almighty God, Just and Civilized Humanity, the Unity of Indonesia, and is inspired by the principle of Social Justice. Its philosophical value is that the state is both an individual and a social being. Deliberation in Indonesian history actually flourished within the Malay cultural tradition of the Islamic era, although a native language flourished on the island of Java called *urun rembug* (sharing ideas in a communal meeting). This tradition was a tradition of deliberation among both commoners and the elite nobility. The term "permusyawaratan" (consultation) reflects the uniqueness of the Indonesian nation in adopting this nation's noble culture, then constructing and institutionalizing it within the political structure by the nation's founders. In practice, of course, it's not just a synonym for "permusyawaratan" (consultation), but rather a political process where the People's Consultative Assembly (MPR) must truly implement deliberation in deciding and establishing a number of political outcomes. (Setyaningsih, 2021)

Deliberation is a political method widely used by Indonesian society, which is a primary practice in the process of conflict resolution and decision-making regarding collective public interests/issues. Deliberation and consensus emphasize the value of resolving problems through open dialogue, respecting the opinions of all parties and prioritizing shared interests, while also avoiding the domination of one party in decision-making. It turns out that this problem-solving model from customary sources that has been running for centuries has been

adopted by the current government, for example in the implementation of the Development Planning Deliberation (Musrenbang) which runs at the village, district/city, provincial and central government levels. In the context of state institutions, this value serves as a principle for the administration of judicial power, aligned with substantive justice and public ethics. The Judicial Commission has the authority to safeguard and uphold the honor, dignity, and behavior of judges, while the Supreme Court has the authority to adjudicate and oversee judicial procedures and the behavior of judges within its institution. The potential for overlapping authority often triggers tension between the Judicial Commission and the Supreme Court, necessitating deliberation and consensus in:

- a. Handling of reports of violations of the code of ethics for judges
- b. Joint policy development regarding judicial supervision

Determination of follow-up steps against judges suspected of violating ethics and discipline. Both elite state institutions between the Judicial Commission and the Supreme Court must be aware and truly understand that the presence of both state institutions is not for the benefit of their respective institutions, but for the benefit of upholding law and justice in this republic, for the benefit of the nation and state, so that whatever thoughts arise if it is for improvement and correction then that is when the statesmanship of the elites, especially the Supreme Court, is needed. Also conversely, the elite of the Judicial Commission must also understand that the Supreme Court is a working partner in order to realize an independent, clean, transparent judicial system in the context of upholding law and justice, therefore the Judicial Commission continues to work professionally and proportionally.

Another effort, of course, is a necessity to build coordination, synchronization, communication and synergy between the elites of the two state institutions in a professional and proportional manner within one paradigm and vision of the nation and state within one state system as stipulated in the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia. Therefore, the value of deliberation and consensus in building the relationship between the Judicial Commission and the Supreme Court is a crucial foundation for achieving integrated, professional, and equitable oversight in accordance with the principles of Pancasila. Both institutions can complement each other in upholding the dignity of the judiciary and strengthening public trust in the judiciary.

2. Integrated Judicial Supervision Model

The synergy of supervision carried out by the Judicial Commission and the Supreme Court has been regulated in the Joint Regulation of the Supreme Court and the Judicial Commission 03/PB/MA/IX/2012 and 03/PB/P.KY//09/2012 concerning the procedures for joint examination of the Chief Justice of the Republic of Indonesia and the Chief Justice of the Republic of Indonesia.

This Joint Regulation is designed to regulate the mechanism for joint examination between the Supreme Court and the Judicial Commission on judges suspected of violating the Code of Ethics and Guidelines for Judges' Conduct (KEPPH), to increase the effectiveness and

coordination in enforcing judges' ethics, and to avoid dualism of supervision in handling alleged ethical violations. In this regulation, what is meant by Joint Examination is a series of activities carried out by a team of examiners to conduct an examination to obtain a conviction whether or not a violation is proven. The Joint Examination Team is a joint team formed by the Supreme Court and the Judicial Commission.

Article 2 paragraph (1) states that a joint examination is carried out in the event of a difference of opinion between the judicial commission and the Supreme Court regarding the Judicial Commission's proposal regarding the results of the examination and/or the imposition of light, medium, or heavy sanctions other than honorable and dishonorable dismissal. Then, paragraph (2) states that a joint examination can be carried out in the event of:

- a. There is the same report submitted or copied to the Supreme Court and the Judicial Commission;
- b. It is known that there is the same problem which is still being examined by the Supreme Court and the Judicial Commission; or
- c. There is information and/or reports that attract public attention and each institution considers it necessary to conduct a joint inspection.

Although this Joint Examination has been regulated, its implementation in the field has encountered obstacles, for example, public reports that have previously been reported to the Supreme Court are often also reported to the Judicial Commission, so that the examination of judges is carried out again, because there is no exchange of complaint information data. This was also mentioned by Mulyadi that it is not uncommon for judges to have to be examined repeatedly by the Supreme Court and examined by the Judicial Commission, which is psychologically unhealthy for judges. In addition, the Supreme Court and the Judicial Commission have never conducted a joint examination due to technical obstacles. (Mulyadi, 2025)

According to the author, the shortcomings of the Joint Regulations of the Supreme Court and the Judicial Commission 03/PB/MA/IX/2021 and 03/PB/P.KY//09/2012 are as follows:

1. Potentially ineffective for urgent cases

There is no standard timeframe for each stage of the joint examination (summons, witness examination, and examination of the accused). This has the potential to delay the judge's ethics examination process, especially if one party is late in responding.

2. Does not provide a deadlock resolution mechanism

If there are differences of opinion between the Supreme Court and the Judicial Commission in assessing the results of a joint examination, there is no mechanism for resolving deadlocks. This could potentially lead to the joint examination stalling without a clear outcome.

3. It does not have strong legal force, so its implementation depends on the leadership of the two state institutions.

Judicial oversight is a crucial component of maintaining the independence, integrity, and accountability of the judiciary. In practice, judicial oversight, conducted by both the Judicial Commission and the Supreme Court, often faces challenges such as overlapping authority, weak coordination, and information gaps between institutions. Therefore, to address these challenges, the author proposes an "Integrated Judicial Supervision Model."

This integrated model of judicial supervision is a response to the complexity of judicial supervision which has so far been separate and carried out independently between the Supreme Court and the Judicial Commission. In addition, this model is also expected to ensure that judicial supervision runs effectively without reducing the independence of judges.

The integrated model of judicial oversight is a system of oversight that combines internal oversight by the Supreme Court with external oversight carried out by the Judicial Commission in a synergistic and coordinated manner. In this model, the Supreme Court continues to carry out its functions of fostering and supervising judicial and administrative technicians, while the Judicial Commission carries out its functions of safeguarding and enforcing the code of ethics and the dignity of judges based on the mandate of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia. The integrated judicial oversight scheme can be described as follows:

Integrated judicial oversight is an effort to create a comprehensive, unified, and effective judicial oversight system while respecting the principle of judicial independence. In the Indonesian context, this oversight is implemented by the Supreme Court as the internal

supervisor and the Judicial Commission as the external supervisor, through a clear coordination mechanism and division of authority.

First, Internal oversight by the Supreme Court is implemented through the Supreme Court Supervisory Body (Bawas MA), focusing on administrative and technical judicial aspects, including judicial discipline, performance, and integrity in carrying out daily duties. The Supreme Court also handles initial investigations into allegations of minor violations committed by judges within the internal authority of the judicial institution.

Second, external oversight by the Judicial Commission focuses on monitoring the behavior and ethics of judges, including receiving public reports regarding alleged violations of the code of ethics and guidelines for judicial conduct. The Judicial Commission conducts an initial investigation of these reports before forwarding them to a joint investigation with the Supreme Court.

Third, within the framework of integrated oversight, the Supreme Court and the Judicial Commission coordinate through the Supreme Court and Judicial Commission Coordination Forum, established under a Joint Regulation of the Supreme Court and the Judicial Commission. This forum serves as a communication and coordination forum for handling reports of alleged judicial misconduct, including determining whether the report will be further processed or dismissed.

Fourth, if there are allegations of serious violations related to the code of ethics of judges, the Judicial Commission and the Supreme Court will form a joint investigation panel to conduct further investigations. This panel consists of elements from the Judicial Commission and the Supreme Court, while prioritizing the principles of independence and objectivity of the investigation.

Fifth, the results of the joint examination will produce recommendations to the Supreme Court regarding the imposition of sanctions on judges proven to have committed violations, whether in the form of reprimands, warnings, demotions, or dismissal, in accordance with the provisions of laws and regulations.

With this integrated approach, judicial oversight by the Supreme Court and the Judicial Commission does not operate in isolation, but rather complements each other, creating a balanced judicial oversight system that protects judicial independence and upholds judicial accountability in the eyes of the public. This model is expected to increase public trust in the judiciary and maintain the dignity and honor of judges as state officials who uphold law and justice.

Through an integrated oversight model, every report of alleged violations of the judicial code of ethics can be followed up with clear coordination. The Judicial Commission receives reports from the public and conducts initial verification. The results are then communicated to the Supreme Court for disciplinary and ethical enforcement review. Conversely, the Supreme Court can provide input on relevant judicial technicalities to the Judicial Commission to support the objectivity of oversight.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

1. Conclusions

The relationship model between these two institutions is based on the coordinative and consultative principles, grounded in the Pancasila values of deliberation and consensus, so that judicial supervision does not overlap and can run effectively and efficiently. In this model, the Supreme Court carries out internal supervision that includes coaching, judicial technical supervision, and judicial administration.

The Judicial Commission carries out external supervision that focuses on maintaining and enforcing the code of ethics and the dignity of judges. This integrated supervision model emphasizes the following principles: Institutional coordination through open and constant communication; Synergy of tasks according to portion of authority; Transparency and accountability in supervision; Non-dualism to avoid conflict of authority between the KY and MA.

This model also implements Pancasila values, especially justice, humanity, and deliberation and consensus in the implementation of judicial supervision, and is relevant to the Pancasila Theory of Justice, which emphasizes the balance between freedom and responsibility, between individual interests and the interests of society.

2. Suggestions

To strengthen the relationship between the Judicial Commission and the Supreme Court, the House of Representatives and the President should immediately revise the Judicial Power Law, the Supreme Court Law, and the Judicial Commission Law, namely by strengthening the relationship between the Judicial Commission and the Supreme Court and the judicial oversight mechanism. To strengthen the regulations for implementing integrated supervision, the Judicial Commission and the Supreme Court should jointly revise or update the joint regulations governing the implementation of judicial supervision, so that they include clear coordination mechanisms, limits of authority, and measurable procedures to prevent overlapping authority, in order to create effective integrated judicial oversight.

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